

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN KNOWLEDGE AND PREGNANCY EXERCISE ACTIVITIES TOWARDS THE INCREASE IN NORMAL DELIVERY IN DJOELHAM REGIONAL PUBLIC HOSPITAL IN 2024

Ida Ria Royentina Sidabukke^{1*}, Julia M Siahaan², Ernawati Barus³,
 Rifiyanti Yuni Arta Silalahi⁴

¹Sari Mutiara Indonesia University (INDONESIA)

²Sari Mutiara Indonesia University (INDONESIA)

³Sari Mutiara Indonesia University (INDONESIA)

⁴Sari Mutiara Indonesia University (INDONESIA)

*Coressponding author: Sidabukeidaria@gmail.com

Abstract

Normal delivery is one of the expectations of mothers after pregnancy, according to the international calendar pregnancy usually lasts 40 weeks, 10 lunar months, or 9 months. The pregnancy process is divided into three trimesters. The first semester is 12 weeks long, the second semester is 15 weeks (weeks 13 to 27), and the third semester is 13 weeks (weeks 28 to 40). Pregnancy planning that requires mental and physical preparation must be done before pregnancy in order to have a positive impact on the mental and physical changes of the mother during pregnancy and the condition of the fetus. As a health worker, it is necessary to teach activities that can increase normal labor, namely by teaching mothers pregnant gymnastics. Maternal health during pregnancy plays a very important role. Because if a mother maintains her health before and during pregnancy, then her baby will be born in normal conditions and the birth of premature babies or low birth weight can be prevented. mothers also need to be taught hypnotherapy methods as pain management to make it easier for mothers to perform normal labor, especially for mothers who do not know how actions can be taken at home and also in health services. One of the hypnotherapies that can help mothers is, using arome therapy that can calm feelings, and can reduce stress levels, there is also a method of giving affirmations to mothers during pregnancy, with the support of the mother's family can communicate well to the mother.

Keywords: Pregnant woman, exercise, normal delivery.

1. INTRODUCTION

The fitness program for pregnant women is to do pregnancy exercises, because pregnancy exercises have special movement principles that are adjusted to the condition of the mother and her pregnancy. Pregnancy exercise exercises should be specifically designed to make pregnant women healthy and fit, reduce complaints that arise during pregnancy, and prepare mothers for childbirth. Exercise will also help mothers to walk upright. As the gestational age increases, the body weight will also be heavier. As a result, the body's balance changes and is centered on the stomach so that when walking pregnant women tend to throw their bodies forward or backward (Muhimah, 2019). Pregnancy exercises are movement exercise therapy to prepare pregnant women, physically or mentally, for fast, safe and spontaneous childbirth. Before starting pregnancy exercises, pregnant women first do warm-up movements so that blood circulation in the body will increase and oxygen transported to the muscles and body tissues will increase, and can reduce the possibility of seizures/injuries because they have been prepared in advance to do more active movements (Yuliarti, 2018). A pregnant mother is advised to do pregnancy exercises, namely after 22 weeks of pregnancy and this age is safe, (Muhimah, 2019). Through pregnancy exercises, a prime condition is obtained by fulfilling the requirements of pregnancy exercises, it is hoped that spiritual and physical freshness can be improved to achieve physiological labor. Pregnancy exercise exercises are preceded by general exercises that aim to increase the body's contraction ability, abdominal wall, and pelvic floor, as well as relax joints and reduce stiffness, muscle and joint pain (Manuaba, 2018).

The positive impact of changes during pregnancy is to support the growth and development of the fetus, while the negative impact is that the mother experiences discomfort during pregnancy. The percentage of discomfort in the first trimester is 50-75% of pregnant women due to nausea and vomiting so that shock often occurs, in the second trimester 50% of pregnant women experience red palms and in the third trimester 60% experience discomfort due to shortness of breath (Lifiana, 2019). Pregnant women are advised to do light exercise during pregnancy so that the mother and fetus are healthier and reduce the problems that arise during pregnancy. Pregnancy exercise is one way that can facilitate the delivery process and help provide relaxation for pregnant women in the third trimester. Pregnant women who participate in pregnancy exercise regularly and intensively will maintain the health of their bodies and the fetus they are carrying optimally (Manuaba, 2018).

The results of previous research conducted by several experts on research on the description of pregnant women's knowledge about pregnancy exercises found that mothers' knowledge was categorized as good due to the high number of pregnant women participating in pregnancy exercises, while respondents who had low knowledge tended not to participate in pregnancy exercise activities. On the other hand, from the results of research conducted by previous researchers, there were still pregnant women who did not perform pregnancy exercises because a person's high knowledge did not necessarily mean that the person was able to apply the knowledge they had. There is a relationship between the mother's knowledge in carrying out pregnancy exercises, high knowledge participating in pregnancy exercises, while respondents who had low knowledge tended not to participate in pregnancy exercise activities. However, when re-examined, there were still pregnant women who did not perform pregnancy exercises because a person's high knowledge did not necessarily mean that the person was able to apply the knowledge they had. There is a relationship between the mother's knowledge in carrying out pregnancy exercises. And the community, and many are organized by hospitals so that spiritual and physical health are improved and can eliminate fear of facing childbirth (Manuaba, 1999). The pregnancy exercises that are applied are not exercises that are oriented only to physical fitness. But to strengthen muscles, flex joints, and most importantly train concentration to divert the mind so that it can forget the pain of childbirth, and strengthen the breath. This method has proven quite successful in helping to ease the labor process. In addition, the pain during the labor process can also be minimized, by regulating breathing, concentrating, and diverting the mind, so that stress during childbirth can be reduced by itself. Then the labor process can run more smoothly and briefly (Mulyata, 2007).

Every mother definitely wants her pregnancy to be safe and comfortable. Regular health checks, a healthy diet, adequate rest, and good stress management are some ways to have a comfortable pregnancy. Mothers should also keep their bodies well hydrated, avoid foods that make them nauseous, and stop smoking and drinking alcohol. According to Aryani (2021) During pregnancy, mothers need more nutrition than non-pregnant women, because the fetus and the fetus itself need nutrition from the mother. If the fetus does not get enough nutrition from the mother, it will absorb the mother's food, causing problems such as the mother becoming weak, pale, having damaged teeth, and losing hair.

In addition, Alfum (2021) said in his panel that babies born with low or no iron stores can experience anemia. The mother may suffer from anemia. Anemia can affect pregnant women by increasing maternal morbidity and mortality, increasing fetal morbidity and mortality, and increasing the risk of low birth weight babies. After nutritional needs are met, mothers also need to be taught the hypnotherapy method as pain management to make it easier for mothers to have normal deliveries, especially for mothers who do not know what actions can be taken at home and also in health services. One of the hypnotherapies that can help mothers is using aromatherapy which can calm feelings and reduce stress levels, there is also a method of providing affirmations to mothers during pregnancy, with the support of the mother's family, they can communicate well with the fetus, with the implementation of pregnancy exercise activities, hypnotherapy, and fulfilling the mother's nutrition can increase efforts for normal delivery.

During the growth and development of pregnancy from month to month, a pregnant woman's ability to adapt to the changes that occur in her physical and mental state is required. These changes occur due to an imbalance of the hormones progesterone and estrogen, namely female hormones that are present in the mother's body since the pregnancy process (Mandriwati, 2008). Pregnancy exercise is a movement exercise therapy given to pregnant women to prepare themselves, both physically and mentally, to face and prepare for a fast, safe, and spontaneous delivery. Pregnancy exercise has begun to receive attention. During the growth and development of pregnancy from month to month, a pregnant woman's ability to adapt to the changes that occur in her physical and mental state is required. These changes occur due to an imbalance of the hormones progesterone and estrogen, namely female hormones that are present in the mother's body since the pregnancy process (Mandriwati, 2008). Pregnancy exercise is a movement exercise therapy given to pregnant women to prepare themselves,

both physically and mentally, to face and prepare for a fast, safe, and spontaneous delivery (Hulliana, 2007).

Eka Mardiana (2022) Pregnancy planning that requires mental and physical preparation must be done before pregnancy in order to have a positive impact on the mother's mental and physical changes during pregnancy as well as the condition of the fetus. Therefore, as health workers, it is necessary to teach activities that can improve normal delivery, namely by teaching mothers pregnancy exercises. Maternal health during pregnancy plays a very important role. Because if a mother maintains her health before and during pregnancy, her baby will be born in normal condition and premature birth or low birth weight can be prevented.

Prenatal exercise has begun to receive attention in the community, and is widely organized by hospitals so that spiritual and physical health are improved and can eliminate fear of facing childbirth (Manuaba, 1999). Prenatal exercise that is applied is not exercise that is oriented only to physical fitness. But to strengthen muscles, flex joints, and mainly train concentration so that it can divert thoughts so that they can forget the pain of childbirth, and strengthen breathing. This method has proven to be quite successful in helping to ease the labor process. In addition, pain during the labor process can also be minimized, by regulating breathing, concentrating, and diverting thoughts, so that stress during childbirth can be reduced by itself. So the labor process can run more smoothly and briefly (Mulyata, 2007). Varney (1997) in Hamilton (2004) explains that prenatal exercise will provide a better pregnancy product or labor outcome, compared to pregnant women who do not do prenatal exercise. Clapp (2005) also explained that mothers who do prenatal exercises during pregnancy are reported to be able to reduce stress in the lead-up to birth, reduce pain during the labor process, have babies born with normal weight, and can reduce the risk of preeclampsia, compared to pregnant women who do not do prenatal exercises during pregnancy.

Based on a preliminary survey conducted at the Dr. RM Djoelham Binjai Regional General Hospital, data was obtained that prenatal exercise classes had been held for pregnant women who were checking their pregnancies. However, of all pregnant women in the third trimester, there were still some who had not attended prenatal exercise. The reason pregnant women did not attend prenatal exercise was mostly because they did not know the benefits of attending prenatal exercise during pregnancy care and did not have time to attend prenatal exercise classes because they had a lot of work at home. Based on the description above, it is necessary to conduct a study entitled "The Relationship between Knowledge and Prenatal Exercise Activities and Normal Childbirth at the Djoelham Binjai Regional General Hospital in 2024".

Eka Mardiana (2022) Pregnancy planning that requires mental and physical preparation must be done before pregnancy in order to have a positive impact on the mother's mental and physical changes during pregnancy as well as the condition of the fetus. Therefore, as health workers, it is necessary to teach activities that can improve normal delivery, namely by teaching mothers pregnancy exercises. Maternal health during pregnancy plays a very important role. Because if a mother maintains her health before and during pregnancy, her baby will be born in normal condition and premature birth or low birth weight can be prevented.

2. METHODOLOGY

The type of research is a form of design used in conducting research procedures. This research is a quasi-experimental research with a nonequivalent control-group design, namely research conducted on two or more groups that are measured before and after treatment. The group of pregnant women is taught to do pregnancy exercises to smooth metabolism and reduce back pain and smooth the labor process.

This study was aimed at all pregnant women who came to visit the Djoelham Binjai Regional General Hospital. According to data obtained from the hospital's medical records, the recapitulation of visits by pregnant women who checked their pregnancies found that the gestational age did not match the height of the uterine fundus and many pregnant women experienced anemia with hemoglobin below normal and experienced back pain and cramps in the lower legs during pregnancy. This requires pregnancy exercises to be done with the aim of helping to reduce the risk during pregnancy and helping the normal delivery process. This study aims to determine the Relationship between Knowledge and Pregnancy Exercise Activities and Normal Childbirth in 2024.

The type of research used is analytic correlation which is intended to test the influence of independent variables on dependent variables (Nursalam, 2011:84). In this study, the relationship between Knowledge and Pregnancy Exercise Activities to Increase Normal Childbirth at Djoelham Binjai

Regional Hospital was analyzed. The research design used by the researcher was cross sectional.

The place of this research was conducted at the Djoelham Binjai Regional Hospital. This research was conducted in January 2024. The population to be used was all pregnant women with a gestational age of more than 22 weeks at the Djoelham Binjai Regional Hospital totaling 28 people. The sample in the study used were pregnant women whose gestational age was more than 22 weeks at the Djoelham Binjai Regional Hospital totaling 28 people. In this study the method used was total sampling. In this study there were two variables, namely: "Independent Variable: knowledge and activity of pregnancy gymnastics while the dependent variable: normal delivery. The instrument used in this study was a questionnaire about pregnancy gymnastics including Understanding pregnancy gymnastics, Requirements for pregnancy gymnastics, Reasons for pregnancy gymnastics, Purpose of pregnancy gymnastics, Benefits of pregnancy gymnastics, Contraindications for pregnancy gymnastics, Instructions for pregnancy gymnastics, Mental preparation for pregnancy gymnastics, Basic movements of pregnancy gymnastics. Assessment for pregnancy gymnastics activities with observation

To find the relationship between knowledge and pregnancy exercise activities to the increase in normal delivery at Djoelham Binjai Regional Hospital, it was calculated using the chi-square test because it uses an ordinal scale and a nominal scale. By using a statistical test computer program using the SPSS 18 for Windows program at a significance level of 0.05 (5%). If $\alpha < 0.05$ then H1 is accepted and H0 is rejected if $\alpha > 0.05$ then H1 is rejected and H0 is accepted.

3. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Bivariate Analysis

3.1.1 Knowledge

Table 5.5 Frequency Distribution of Knowledge of Pregnant Women at Djoelham Binjai Regional Hospital

No	Knowledge	Frequency	Percentage
1	Good	15	53.6
2	Enough	10	35.7
3	Not enough		10.7
TOTAL		28	100

Source: primary research data 2024

Based on table 5.5 above, it is known that 15 pregnant women (53.6%) have good knowledge, 10 pregnant women (35.7%) have sufficient knowledge, and 3 pregnant women (10.7%) have poor knowledge. Knowledge is the result of knowing and this happens when someone senses a particular object. Sensing occurs through the five human senses, namely the senses of sight, hearing, smell, taste and touch. Most human knowledge is obtained through the eyes and ears. Explaining that knowledge includes six levels of cognitive domains, namely knowing, understanding, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation. Factors that influence the level of knowledge include internal factors: education (knowledge), work, age. And external factors: environment and socio-culture (Notoatmodjo, 2007: 139). So that mothers are expected to always play an active role in the knowledge and skills of pregnancy exercises for pregnant women.

3.1.2 Pregnancy Exercise Activities

Pregnancy exercise at Djoelham Binjai Regional Hospital			
No	Activity Prenatal Gymnastics	Frequency	Percentage
1	Active	22	78,6
2	Inactive	6	21,4
Total		28	100

Source: primary research data 2024

Based on table 5.6 above, it is known that the majority of 22 pregnant women (78.6%) are active in pregnancy exercises, and a small proportion of 6 pregnant women (21.4%) are not active in pregnancy exercises. According to Suharso (2005: 9) Activeness comes from the word active which means active, persistent, dynamic, and energetic or as opposed to static or symbolic and has a tendency

to spread or develop. And (Nurdia, 2010: 2) Activeness is a behavior that can be seen from the regularity and involvement of a person to be active in activities. The activeness of pregnant women in pregnancy exercise activities is influenced by various factors including: mother's education, mother's job, family income level, mother's knowledge, mother's age, number of children, distance from the integrated health post and supporting facilities. So it is hoped that to increase activeness in participating in pregnancy exercise, it is hoped that with the participation of the entire community, and health cadres can increase the activeness of mothers in pregnancy exercise activities. The Relationship between Pregnant Women's Knowledge about Pregnant Women's Gymnastics Activities and Normal Delivery at Djoelham Binjai Regional Hospital in January 2024

3.1.3 Chi-Square Tests

Value	df	Asymp.	Sig.(2-sided)
Participate in prenatal exercise activities to provide and improve			
Pearson		Chi-Square	
4,387a		2,112	
Likelihood Ratio 3.7562.153			
3,289	1,070		

There is no relationship between pregnant women's knowledge about pregnancy exercises and N of Valid Cases 28

Based on the results of the Chi-Square Tests statistical test calculation, the results obtained were that $p = 0.112$ with a significance of more than 0.05 which means (not significant). If $\alpha < 0.05$ then H_1 is accepted and H_0 is rejected, meaning that there is a relationship, if $\alpha > 0.05$ then H_1 is rejected and H_0 is accepted, meaning that there is no relationship between pregnant women's knowledge about pregnancy exercise activities and normal delivery at the Djoelham Binjai Regional Hospital in January 2024

Lack of knowledge is an important factor in the problem of inactivity of pregnant women in participating in pregnancy exercise because of their lack of self-confidence and health cadres apply their knowledge and are less able to apply counseling information in everyday life (Sutrismang, 2010). So it is expected that health workers provide information to pregnant women who are there to participate in pregnancy exercise activities before the activity is carried out 1 week before to remind pregnant women, motivate pregnant women, and increase the activity of pregnant women in pregnancy exercise activities at the Djoelham Binjai Regional Hospital.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results and discussion, it can be concluded that:

- The majority of pregnant women's knowledge about pregnancy exercises at the Djoelham Binjai Regional Hospital, 15 pregnant women (53.6%) had good knowledge.
- The activeness of pregnant women in participating in pregnancy exercise activities at the Djoelham Binjai Regional Hospital, the majority of 22 pregnant women (78.6%) were active in participating in pregnancy exercise.
- There is a Relationship between Mother's Knowledge and Increased Normal Delivery
- There is a relationship between prenatal exercise activities and increasing normal delivery.

The activity of pregnancy exercise at Djoelham Binjai Regional Hospital can be seen from the results of the analysis using the Chi-Square Tests statistical test. with a significance level of 0.05, namely $p = 0.112$ so that $p > \alpha 0.05$, then H_1 is rejected and H_0 is accept the activity of pregnancy exercise at Djoelham Binjai Regional General Hospital can be seen from the results of the analysis using the Chi-Square Tests statistical test. with a significance level of 0.05, namely $p = 0.112$ so that $p > \alpha 0.05$, then H_1 is rejected and H_0 is accepted.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND SUGGESTION

For Health Workers, this research is expected to be able to increase knowledge and abilities in developing skills for the Community in the midst of the era of globalization in the health sector in general and midwifery in particular.

For the Research Site, with this research, it can be used as input and to improve health services so that they can always provide better supervision for pregnant women, especially knowledge about routine pregnancy exercise activities 2-3 times a week with the aim of increasing normal delivery.

For pregnant women, with this research, it is hoped that they can continue to increase their knowledge, continue to learn and routinely do pregnancy exercise activities and always come to health services to get health information about the importance of doing exercise activities in improving the health of their pregnancy and helping to improve normal delivery.

REFERENCES

- [1] Alwi, Hasan, et al. 2002. Big Indonesian Dictionary, Third Edition. Jakarta: Ministry of National Education Balai Pustaka Anonymous. 2014. Stages During Pregnancy,(Online).(http://www//rumahbunda.com// Accessed on Tuesday 13 October 2015).
- [2] Arikunto, Suharsimi. 2010. Research Procedures: A Practical Approach. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- [3] Arikunto, Suharsimi. 2006. Research Procedures: A Practical Approach. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- [4] Statistics Agency of North Sumatra 2015. Statistics of Binjai Ponorogo Regency: Binjai City
- [5] Bandiyah, Siti. 2009. Pregnancy, Labor and Labor Disorders. Yogyakarta: Nuha Medika
- [6] Ministry of Health.2012.Inhttp://ontar.ui.ac.id/file?file=digital/20280672-T%20Eli%20Rusmita.pdf. Accessed Tuesday, October 13, 2015
- [7] Effendi, N. 1998. Basics of Community Nursing. Jakarta: EGC
- [8] Hidayat, Aziz Alimul. 2010. Midwifery Research Methods Data Analysis Techniques. Jakarta: Salemba Medika.
- [9] Indarti, et al. 2013. Pregnancy Babon Book.Yogyakarta:INDOLITERACY
- [10] Kartono, K. 1992. Psychology of Women. Bandung: Mandar Maju.
- [11] Manuaba, IBG. 1998. Obstetrics, Gynecological Diseases, and Family Planning. Jakarta: EGC.
- [12] Manuaba Ida Bagus G. 2009. Understanding Women's Reproductive Health. Jakarta: Arcan
- [13] Maryunani, Anik, et al. 2010. Pregnancy exercise, postpartum exercise and music therapy. Jakarta
- [14] Nasir, Abdul, et al. 2011. Textbook "Health Research Methods". Yogyakarta: Nuha Medika
- [15] Notoatmodjo, Soekidjo. 2005. Health Research Methodology. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta
- [16] Notoatmodjo, Soekidjo. 2007. Health Promotion and Behavioral Science. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta
Nurdia, Dewi. (On line),(http://digilib.unimus.ac.id/files/disk1/105/jtptunimus-gdl-dewinurdia-5208-3-bab2.pdf, Accessed Tuesday, October 13, 2015.)
- [17] Nursalam. 2011. Concept and Application of Nursing Science Research Methodology "Guidelines for Nursing Research Thesis and Instruments. Jakarta: Salemba Medika
- [18] Prawirohardjo, Sarwono, et al. 2009. Obstetrics: Jakarta: YBPSP
- [19] Riskesdas. 2013. Basic Health Research "Riskesdas 2013" Ministry of the Republic of Indonesia.
- [20] Rustam, Mochtar. 1998. Synopsis of Obstetrics, Operative Obstetrics, Social Obstetrics. Jakarta: EGC
- [21] Wulandari, Ita Y. 2006. In the journal:
http://journal.unair.ac.id/filerPDF/05%20Effectiveness%20of%20Pregnancy%20Sena%20as%2

0Prenatal%20Service%20in%20Reducing%20Anxiety%20Facing%20First%20Delivery.pdf.

Accessed Tuesday, October 13, 2015